

Motivation and Anxiety as Predictors of Students' Academic Achievement in Junior Secondary School in Basic Science in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

This study investigated motivation and anxiety as predictors of students' academic achievement in junior secondary school in Basic Science in Ekiti State. The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between students' anxiety and motivation on academic performance in Basic Science. Also to investigate the the level of secondary school students' academic achievement in Basic Science in Ekiti State. The study adopted descriptive survey and expo-facto research design. The targeted population for the study consisted all the 16,256 Junior Secondary Schools (JSS) three students in all 209 public secondary schools across the 16 Local Government Areas of Ekiti State as at the time of the study and the sample for the study

consisted of 240 JSS 3 students selected from the three Senatorial Districts of Ekiti State using multistage sampling procedure. Two instruments titled; "Students' Variables Questionnaire (SVQ)" and "Inventory on Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (IJSSCE)" were used for collection of data for the study. Face and content validities of SVQ was ensured through experts in Tests and Measurement, Science Education and Psychology. Test-retest method was used to establish reliability coefficient of 0.89 for SVQ. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Specifically, research question was analysed using frequency count and percentage, hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis showed that the level of secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State was moderate and that there was significant relationship between both students' anxiety and motivation on academic performance in Basic Science. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Students' variables such as anxiety and motivation were important factors that influence academic performance in Basic Science. It was therefore recommended that Basic Science teaching stake holders should raise public awareness of the crippling influence of anxiety and motivation on students' academic

performance in Basic Science, school counsellors should work with the Ministry of Education to develop and implement public education programmes.

Keywords: *Motivation, Anxiety, Predictors, Students' Academic Achievement, Basic Science.*

Introduction

Today's world uses science as a key indication of progress, with the United States of America, Russia, China, and Japan being seen as developed nations due to their advancements in science (Agbaje & Alake, 2014). Rather than just knowing how science works, it is about using that knowledge to address human needs via action.

People may find it difficult to function well without a basic understanding of science, since the world operates on a scientific basis in both thought and behaviour. The degree of scientific and technological advancement in a country determines its overall growth. Because science is so important to people's lives and to society as a whole, it has become an invaluable instrument. According to Adodo and Oyeniyi (2013), science is the methodical observation and experimentation of the phenomena and events that surround us. In other words, science is a methodical process that leads pupils from a general curiosity in the world to the formation of scientific thought.

Without science education, science technology in its whole and the related abilities it requires cannot be accomplished. According to Batomalaque (2015), science education is the teaching and learning of science with the goal of gaining a practical grasp of scientific ideas and principles related to real-world circumstances as well as the scientific skills, values, and attitudes required to analyse and solve everyday issues. Science aids in brain growth and, as a result, produces fresh information that helps quell curiosity about how the world comes into being. Oredein and Awodun (2013) assert that extensive scientific information about national revenue, military might, and the nation's standing internationally has contributed to the development of national pride and prestige throughout time. They went on to say that

research has produced cutting-edge apps and microcomputers, which have given industrialised nations the aforementioned national prestige.

Additionally, science provides a deeper comprehension of the environment in which we live, leading to the discovery of many necessities for daily living, like electricity, cell phones, the internet, Facebook, refrigerators, televisions, and cars, among other things. The emergence of science and technology has led to a significant decrease in the number of hospital deaths, which has implications for the medical industry. Young kids have been inspired to study and pursue careers in science by the fascinating materials and experiences that science has to offer. Students who get science education are equipped with the information and abilities necessary to thrive in both the classroom and in society at large. This includes critical thinking, problem-solving, and technological literacy. Although it is evident that science and technology have significantly improved living circumstances worldwide, junior secondary schools (JSS) do not adequately educate and learn about these topics. A key factor in a country's growth is science. Because of this, it is impossible to overstate the contribution that science and technology provide to improving a society's quality of living and level of the labour force.

The Federal Government of Nigeria developed the 6-3-3-4 policy on education in the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2004) in an effort to promote science education. This policy states that a child should spend six years in primary school, three years in JSS, three years in SSS, and four years in university. The Federal Government of Nigeria evaluated this educational system in 2012 and developed the 9-3-4 system, which mandates that a kid attend elementary school for nine years until they reach

the JSS level, then spend three years at the SSS and four years in university.

It became necessary to review, reorganise, and realign the current Primary and JSS curricula to fit into a 9-year Basic Education Programme after the Federal Government decided to implement a 9-year programme. This was due to the need to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by 2015 and, consequently, the need to implement the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS) (Obioma, 2012). This has an impact on JSS-level course offerings. Basic Science (JSS 1-3) replaced the JSS Integrated Science course (Danmole, 2011). As a result, curriculum were created for these courses as well. According to Danmole (2011), the main goals of the new Basic Science and Technology curriculum are to provide students with the following abilities: to cultivate an interest in science and technology; to gain a foundational understanding of science and technology; to apply science and technology knowledge and skills to meet societal needs; to take advantage of the many career opportunities provided by science and technology; and to get ready for further scientific study.

More focus has to be placed on the quality of scientific education, including the teaching of topics like biology and basic science, if a nation is to prosper from science and technology. All of the fundamental scientific courses, including physics, chemistry, biology, mathematics, and technology, are included in the category of basic science. It is an interdisciplinary topic that is essential to all areas of scientific education. Therefore, no student should be excluded from receiving an appropriate education in fundamental science at the elementary level in Primary and Junior Secondary schools.

A prerequisite and foundational topic in junior secondary education is basic science. For students to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the scientific courses, basic science teaches science as a cohesive method (Oniya, 2018). Regarding its idea and goals as an academic discipline, instructors approach this topic with a broader perspective. Basic science

knowledge is required for people to get scientific training in a variety of fields. It also aids in the scientific and technical advancement of the country. According to Joseph and Okere (2018), basic science is the first science that facilitates an all-encompassing study of scientific subjects.

The goals of basic science are to help students become interested in science and technology, as well as to provide them with the fundamental knowledge and skills they need to meet human needs and pursue further studies in these fields (Joseph and Okere, 2018).

Teaching and studying the fundamental approach, or the methodical process of doing research on the living and non-living objects in our surroundings, is known as basic science education. Prior to its rebranding as Basic Science, Integrated Science was a required science course for high school students. In Nigeria, a student studying basic science at the JSS level is prepared to study core scientific topics at the Senior Secondary School (SSS) level. This demonstrates that a kid has to have a solid foundation in basic science at the JSS level before they may study any scientific topic at the SSS level. Because of this, the Junior Secondary School curriculum places a strong emphasis on Basic Science.

The lack of practical activities in Basic Science has resulted in poor manipulation and observation skills in students, and the absence of these expected skills in students gave rise to the students' poor performance in Basic Science subject, which made it not encouraging to the students (Oniya, 2018). This is true despite the utilitarian value of Basic Science in science and technological advancement and teachers' role in the realization of these objectives. A large number of recent high school graduates who have little value as human resources may be unleashed into the system if the tendency is allowed to continue. Through student interviews, the researcher—a secondary school basic science teacher—observed that pupils shun basic science because of its abstract character.

The researcher found that in-depth empirical study is necessary to comprehend the dynamics

and complexity of variables that impact students' academic accomplishment in order to solve the urgent need to improve Nigeria's poor academic performance at this level of science.

According to the Ekiti State Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology (2013), despite the significant contributions science makes to national development and government efforts to enhance science education, student

performance in internal junior examinations appears to be unsatisfactory, and this is reflected in the results that most certificate awarding examination bodies, including WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB, have not been satisfied with.

For instance, Table 1 displays the academic achievement of pupils in Ekiti state's Basic Science on the public Junior Secondary School Certificate test from 2019 to 2021.

Table 1. Academic Performance of Students in Basic Science in Public JSSCE in Ekiti State from 2019-2021

Year	Distinction		Credit		Pass		Failed		Absent		Total
2019	1789	8.3%	7784	35.9%	1139	52.6%	516	2.4%	201	0.8%	21,685
2020	2065	10.7%	6223	32.4%	9658	50.2%	1096	5.7%	185	1.0%	19,227
2021	1563	8.4%	7607	40.8%	8768	47.1%	480	2.6%	205	1.1%	18,623

Source: Research and statistics unit, Ekiti state ministry of education

It has been noted that just 8.35% of students who took the test in 2019 received distinction, compared to almost 50% of students who passed. Merely 43.1% of the total students who took the test in 2020 could be deemed to have achieved a minimum credit level performance. 8.4% of enrolled students in 2021 received distinction and credit. This data demonstrates that fundamental science student performance has not been positive.

The researcher saw that many different teaching strategies had been tried out with students who claimed to have slightly improved academic performance in basic science. These could be due to a variety of factors, including the students' motivation, anxiety, and family background as well as factors like gender differences, attitude towards science learning, and lack of qualified teachers, instructional materials, and lab facilities (Adodo and Oyeniyi, 2013). The researcher was of interest to examine the determinant of anxiety and motivation on academic achievement of junior secondary school Basic Science students.

One way to define anxiety is a feeling of fear towards a certain circumstance. Because of their illogical dread and unfavourable emotional response when asked to solve problems and engage in scientific practicals, students' anxiety has also been linked to their failure in science

classes. One of the main causes of the students' disinterest in science has been their concern about the topic. A few of the main reasons why science students get anxious include feeling that the science curriculum is too broad, finding it hard to understand, thinking that there are more science major failures than passing grades, being afraid of science labs, teachers not being creative or encouraging, not having enough teaching resources, etc. Woldemanuel, Atagana, and Engida (2013) claimed that students' academic achievement in Basic Science may be influenced by characteristics such as gender, interest, and attitude. Olubunmi (2016) found that whereas guys sought employment in management, engineering, finance, and other brain-twisting fields, ladies tended to enrol in courses that don't demand much energy or mental strain, including homemaking. Motivation is "a reason for doing something," or that which makes someone desire to do something, according to Hornby (2010). In these notions, "motivation" refers to the actions that students do to understand science. Given the above rationale, motivation is what sparks pupils' interest in studying.

An individual's needs, desires, wants, or urges are what drive them. Motivation in the context of basic science is the process of igniting an interest in and drive to solve practical and

scientific challenges. In order to foster and maintain a lifetime interest in scientific topics that may be relevant to fundamental science, motivation is essential. Stated differently, pupils' positive interest in science might be considered motivation. Teachers are crucial in stimulating students' enthusiasm in science and technology courses. This may be accomplished by providing guidance to the students and creating an engaging learning environment to encourage active participation in class activities. A suitable relationship between the instructor and students during classroom engagement is necessary for the development and maintenance of interest. The verb motivate implies to provoke or excite.

Statement of the Problem

Despite various efforts by stakeholders to improve teaching and learning of Basic science in Junior Secondary Schools because of its central role in building solid foundation to Science Education and technological advancement. It is still characterized by low enrollment of students as a result of view it as a difficult subject to pass and comprehend. The academic performance of students both in external and internal examinations has not been encouraging which might be as a result of Basic Science teachers that are still using conventional method to teach the subject.

The researcher observed that variables such as motivation and anxiety could also be predictors of the performance of students in the subject. Therefore, the study investigated the impact of motivation and anxiety on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Basic Science in Ekiti State.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated motivation and anxiety as predictors of students' academic achievement in junior secondary school in Basic Science in Ekiti State.

Research Question

One research question was raised to guide the study

1. What is the level of secondary school students' academic achievement in Basic Science in Ekiti State?

Research Hypotheses

Two research hypotheses were postulated for the study;

1. There is no significant relationship between students' anxiety and academic performance in Basic Science.
2. There is no significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance in Basic Science.

Significance of the Study

Teachers, students, parents, curriculum designers, the government, other researchers, and society as large would all benefit from the study's conclusions. The study's findings will help JSS basic science teachers better understand the motivations and anxieties that students have about learning basic science. With this understanding, they will be able to use that knowledge to help students perform better academically in basic science.

Curriculum planners, teachers workshop and seminar organisers, and the government would find value in the study's findings as they provide evidence of how students' motivation and anxiety predict academic performance in Basic Science and how to design curriculum around these variables to enhance academic performance. If the research's findings are put into practice, parents may also profit as, given the factors the study identified, kids who learn basic science and technology will probably do better in basic science classes.

Given that most parents are aware of the value of science, this might act as a catalyst for them to increase their financial commitment to their kids' education. Because it will act as a launching pad for further research, the study's findings will also be helpful to aspiring researchers.

Delimitation of the Study

The study was delimited to motivation and anxiety as predictors of students' academic achievement in junior secondary school in basic

science in Ekiti state. Only public JSS 3 pupils who took part in the 2023 Ekiti State Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (JSSCE) were included in the research.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in the study was an expo-facto and descriptive survey.

Population

The population consisted of all 16,256 Junior Secondary Schools (JSS) three students in all 209 public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample consisted of 240 JSS 3 students who were chosen using a multi-stage sampling technique. Stage one was the use of simple random sampling technique to select a Local Government from each of the three senatorial districts in Ekiti State. In stage two, two secondary schools from each of the local government areas were chosen using the purposive sample technique with the consideration of gender mixed-school and schools with teachers who are integrated science university degrees. Stage three was the chosen of an intact class of an arm from JSS3 from the school selected.

Research Instruments

Two instruments used were the "Students' Variables Questionnaire (SVQ)" and the "Inventory on Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (IJSSCE)."

SVQ contains two sections; A and B, in which section A contained bio-data of the students while section B contained five items on students' motivation and anxiety as predictors of academic achievement in Basic Science in junior secondary schools. The scores for the items in this portion of the questionnaire included four alternatives ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree on a 4-point Likert style scale: Agree - 3, Strongly Disagree - 1, and Strongly Agree - 4.

IJSSCE was used to collect raw scores of each basic science students that took part in 2023 Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination.

Validity of the Instrument

The SVQ's face and content validity were ascertained with the help of two specialists in each of the areas; Psychology, Guidance and Counselling and Test and Measurement.

Reliability of the Instrument

The test-retest method was used to establish SVQ by given it to twenty JSS 3 basic science students from outside the sampled local government areas twice at the interval of two weeks. Scores collected from the two tests were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the reliability coefficient of 0.89 was obtained which was used to adjudge the instrument to be reliable.

Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study question was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentage, and all of the hypotheses were examined using inferential statistics. To be more precise, the t-test was used to test hypothesis 6 and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypotheses 1 through 5. Every hypothesis was examined at the significance level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question

What is the level of secondary school students' academic achievement in Basic Science in Ekiti State?

The Ekiti State Ministry of Education provided the JSSCE results for the secondary schools in the state, which were used to analyse the question. The percentile distribution method was used to establish the three student variable levels—low, moderate, and high—at secondary schools located in Ekiti State. Respondents who scored 66.6% (53.28) of the total score and above on the "Students' Variables Questionnaire

(SVQ)" were classified as having "high" students' variables in secondary schools, while those who scored 33.3 percent (26.64) of the total scores on students' variables in secondary schools and below were classified as having "low" students' variables in secondary schools. The "moderate" level of students' variables in secondary schools was defined as scores between the low and high student groups' variables. Table 3 displays the academic achievement of Ekiti State secondary school pupils in Basic Science.

Table 1. Level of Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State

Students' academic performance	Frequency	Percentage
Distinction	51	21.4
Credit	133	55.5
Pass	41	17.1
Fail	15	6.1
Total	240	100.0

The academic achievement of Ekiti State secondary school pupils in Basic Science is shown in Table 1 and Figure I. Out of 240 pupils, the results indicate that 51 (representing 21.4%) had a Distinction, 133 (55.5%) had Credit, 41 (17.1%) had a Pass, and 15 (6.1%) had a Failure. As a result, Ekiti State's secondary school pupils perform academically at a middling level in Basic Science. Therefore, the level of

Table 2. Students' Anxiety and Academic Performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	P
Students' anxiety	240	14.04	3.56	0.508*	0.000
Academic performance	240	57.44	21.61		

Note: * $p < 0.05$

The hypothesis was tested by calculating the scores for students' anxiety using questions 11–15 in Section B of the "Students' Variables Questionnaire (SVQ)" and obtaining the academic record of the school-based assessment for Basic Science. Following that, a statistical analysis using Pearson Product Moment

secondary school students' academic achievement in Basic Science in Ekiti State was moderate.

Figure 1. Level of secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State

Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant relationship between students' anxiety and academic performance in Basic Science.

Correlation was performed on these sets of scores at the significance level of 0.05. The result is shown in Table 2.

The estimated r-value (-0.508) is significant at the $p < 0.05$ threshold of significance, as Table 6 demonstrates. We reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that anxiety levels among students

and their academic achievement in basic science in Ekiti State are significantly correlated. In Ekiti State, there is a moderate and statistically significant negative association between students' anxiety and their academic achievement in Basic Science.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance in Basic Science.

The Students' Variables Questionnaire (SVQ) Section B's questions 16–20 were used to calculate scores related to students' motivation, and the school-based examination record had information about their academic achievement in Basic Science. These data were used to test the hypothesis. Following that, a statistical analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was performed on these sets of scores at the significance level of 0.05. Table 3 displays the outcome.

Table 3 Students' Motivation and Academic Performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	P
Students' anxiety	240	14.08	3.50	0.563*	0.000
Academic performance	250	57.44	21.61		

Note: * $p < 0.05$

Table 3 shows that the computed r-value (0.563) is significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State. The correlation between students' motivation and academic performance in Basic Science in Ekiti State is moderate and statistically significant in a positive direction.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that the level of secondary school students' academic achievement in Basic Science was moderate. This might be that Basic Science teachers succeeded through their regular and extracurricular activities towards the examination. Students will do well academically when teaching and learning activities in the schools are conducted and done in an environment that favours learning. This is agreement with Dike (2014) who argued that creating a curriculum is not enough; what's really important is putting in place the mechanisms that will ensure that its goals can be accomplished via effective teaching process.

The findings of the research showed that anxiety levels among students and their academic achievement in basic science in Ekiti State are significantly correlated. It is of the opinion of the researcher that students' negative emotional reactions and illogical fear cause them to lose interest in and do poorly in science subject such as Basic Science. This result is consistent with a research by Mazzone et al. (2017) that found anxiety symptoms may lead to poor academic performance and academic failure because they are linked to memory and cognitive function impairment. Chronic anxiety has a negative impact on academic achievement, according to Iris (2011).

The research discovered a strong correlation between students' motivation and academic achievement of students in basic science. This means that if fostering or cultivating students' enthusiasm is focused, it is likely that achievement in basic science would be improved. The result is similar to a research conducted in 2015 by Haider et al., which discovered a favourable statistically significant association between academic achievement and both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The result is also in agreement to Amrai, Motlagh, Zalani, and Parhon (2011), who stated that a

variety of motivating variables work together to influence students' academic success.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it could be concluded that academic achievement of secondary school students in Basic Science was modest. Also that academic performance in Basic Science was significantly impacted by students' characteristics which includes motivation, and anxiety.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. The government and other parties involved in education (such as NGOs, philanthropists, school administrators, and parents) should work together to increase academic performance above the current level by demonstrating a stronger commitment to providing an atmosphere such as well-equipped laboratory and conducive classroom that will encourage effective teaching and learning process.
2. To raise public awareness of the crippling effects of anxiety on students' academic performance in Basic Science, school counsellors should work with the Ministry of Education to develop and implement public education programmes.
3. For improved academic achievement, basic science instructors and parents should use suitable motivating techniques such reinforcement and parental engagement in their children's school activities.

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